

**FEEDING OF DOMESTIC BREEDED BULLS WITH PROTEIN-RICH
GRANULAR FEED PRODUCT MADE FROM "WALNUT, CLOVER,
AMARANTH" PRODUCTS.**

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Keywords: Cattle breeding is the leading branch of animal husbandry, providing the population with milk and meat products, leather raw materials for light industry, and organic fertilizers for agriculture.

ABSTRACT

This industry provides 97% of the world's milk demand, and 50% of its meat demand. This indicator corresponds to 99% and 65% in Uzbekistan, respectively. Bulls need to be properly fed to gain high weight. Most farmers distribute the feed three times at the same time interval. From the postpartum period to 60 days, calves are fed milk, then wheat groats and quality hay are added. Such feeding promotes rapid growth and eliminates problems with the digestive system. From 60 to 90 days, feed products with a high protein content, which help to increase body mass, are the basis of the diet, preference is given. This includes vegetable crops, ground grain. From 120 days, an additional 10-15 kg of soaked green grass is given.

Professor P. N. Kuleshov (1949) stated that the amount and quality of feed given to certain types of animals is also important. The development of rapid growth and fat accumulation creates a carnivorous animal. In order to produce cheap beef, calves should be intensively fed during the first 6-8 months of their life. Even now, the role of feeding in the improvement of breeds of agricultural animals of various types, in the creation of new systems and types of them, productive herds, in revealing the effectiveness of crossbreeding, has been determined in the results of scientific production studies conducted in various ecological regions.

According to V. Kalashnikov, Kh. Amerkhanov (2005), N. I. Strekozov, G. P. Legoshin (2005), Yu. Kotlyarov, N. Klunduk (2005) and others, full value feeding of cattle increases their genetic potential for productivity is an important factor in the output. Similar conclusions were made by K.K. Karibaev (1999), A. Kharlamov, A. Irsultanov (2001), N.I. Ivanova (2004) also came.

Sh.A. Akmalkhanov (1993), U. Nosirov (1974, 2000), M. Ashirov (1994), K. Karibaev (1996), L.K. Ernst (2001), A.V. According to Cherekaev (2001), Kh. Amerkhanov (2004) and other well-known scientists, the milk yield of feed cattle is 60-70% and the meat yield is 60-62% depending on feeding, its level and total cost. It is clear from these points that feeding is the main factor in bringing out economic beneficial characteristics of cattle

In the research of S.S. Ibragimov (1991), it was found that growing Bushuev and Holsteinized black-Ola calves under conditions of full-value feeding allowed them to increase their live weight by 13-14 times from birth to 18 months, and they gained 7.25-7.25 per 1 kg of live weight. He stated that he spent 7.55 kg of food

There are many factors that influence the full development of the genetic potential of bulls fed to the fattening area in terms of meat production. The main and most important of these is to feed them with full value. In our experiment on Holstein bulls at the farm "Tashpolatov Bahadir Zhoraniyozovich" in Sherabod district, we obtained the following results when we fed them with granulated feed made from "Yantok, beda, amaranth" products, rich in oxygen.

It should be noted that protein is one of the most important substances involved in the formation of new tissues and organs in the growing body of bulls. As the age of animals increases, the consumption of protein per living unit decreases. If the amount of protein in the diet is insufficient, the nutrients are not fully consumed, as a result, growth and development are slowed down. It has been found that when the amount of protein exceeds the norm, the appetite of animals deteriorates and growth lags behind. The reason for this is that most of the nitrogen is excreted in feces and urine. In this case, the amount of protein in the live weight increases, while fat decreases. In order to prevent such negative consequences, we paid special attention to the amount of digestible protein when feeding animals. For this, we can learn from our experience

**Feed consumed by bulls during the experiment is kg
(average per head)**

Table 1.

№	Foods and their nutrition	Amount of food given to bulls (6 months).									
		Amount of food in kg	Feed unit kg	Total food unitkg	AEM	fat g	Klechatka g	Protein g	Dry matter g	Ca g	P g
1	Milk	4	0.30	1.2	200	148	-	132	520	4.8	5.3
2	Blue clover	3	0.21	0.63	333	24	243	120	840	14.1	0.21
3	Senej	2	0.35	0.70	296	68	254	142	900	22	2.0
4	Alfalfa hay	2	0.44	0.88	660	44	506	202	1660	34	4.4
5	"Yantok, alfalfa" granulated fodder product	3	1.0	3.0							
6	Table salt										
	Total			6.41	1489	284	1003	596	3886	74.9	11.91

The amount of digested protein in the actual consumer product of the bull experiment was 460.6 kg, 116 grams of digested protein per 11 kg volume unit.

In the organization of complete feeding of animals, we paid attention to the amount of energy, carbohydrates and mineral substances in the feed, as well as the relationship of certain substances in the course of processes, the level of absorption and excretion of food, and the body of accumulation. Our obtained data correspond to the norms recommended by A.P. Kalashnikov and others (1986), R. Hamrokulov, K. Karibaevlar (1999).

The fodder given to the bulls in the experiment differed not only in its quantity, but also in its nutrient composition. We do it

We can find out from Table 2.

Summary.

Concentrated feeds play an important role in feeding cattle fed for meat on the basis of standards and delivering high-quality beef from them. Therefore, we have standardized the amount of this type of food in the ration, taking into account the period

of growth of animals. Let's say that in terms of nutritional content, the total feed consumed in the initial period of growth, i.e. from birth to 6 months of concentrate feed, was around 25.0-29.0 percent, this figure at the end of the experiment was during the final weaning period, it is doubled and reaches 50-58%. In general, if we add the granulated fodder product "Alfalfa, alfalfa and amaranth" to the ration of bulls, fattening of bulls is faster and economically cheaper. this indicates that their feeding conditions are organized in the same way.

Thus, in our research, when Holstein bulls were given a feed with significantly higher nutritive value, "Alfalfa, alfalfa and amaranth" granulated feed, it was considered an important factor in ensuring their rapid growth and high productivity.

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